

Thioamide Bands and Nature of Bonding in Complexes of 3-(4-Pyridyl)Triazoline-5-Thione with Non-Transition Metals

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Complexes of 3-(4-pyridyl)triazoline-5-thione have been prepared with Pb(II), Mg(II), Sn(II), As(V), Sb(III) and Bi(III) and characterised using various physico-chemical methods such as chemical method as well as near and far infrared spectroscopy. The complexes have the molecular formula $[Pb(3,4PT5TH)_2(H_2O)_2](NO_3)_2$, $[Mg(3,4PT5TH)_2(H_2O)_4]Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$, $[Sn(3,4PT5TH)_2(OH)_2]$, $[Sn(3,4PT5TH)_4(OH)_2]$, $[Sb(3,4PT5TH)_2Cl_2]$, $[Bi(3,4PT5TH)(H_2O)Cl_2]$ and $[As(C_{11}H_{13}N_4OS)_2]$. Probable structures have been assigned to these complexes and the modes of metal-ligand bonding have been investigated. In all these complexes, bonding is through thiocarbonyl sulphur. This results in splittings of thioamide bands I, II and III and red shifting of thioamide band IV. All the split bands are observed at higher frequencies. Metal-ligand vibrations have also been assigned.

COMPLEXES of 3-(4-pyridyl)triazoline-5-thione¹ with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Pd(II), Pt(II), Pt(IV), Rh(III) and Rh(I), Tl(I) and Au(I) have been studied and reported²⁻⁴ earlier. In most of them coordination occurs through nitrogen as well as sulphur but in Tl(I) and Au(I) complexes⁵ coordination occurs only through nitrogen. In the present paper we are reporting the complexing behaviour of this ligand with non-transition metal ions such as Pb(II), Sn(II), Mg(II), As(V), Sb(III) and Bi(III). Metal-ligand stretching modes of the complexes have also been investigated using far infrared spectroscopy. Use of ν_{NH} band and the four thioamide bands⁶⁻⁹ of the ligand has been made to decide the nature of bonding in the complexes.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of 'AnalaR' grade. The ligand was prepared by the method of Dutta *et al.*¹. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen estimations were done by the microanalytical section of the I. I. T., Kanpur.

Infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in KBr pellets using Perkin-Elmer 377 infrared spectrometer. Calibration was done using a polystyrene film.

Preparation of complexes: The complexes were prepared by the following general methods.

About 0.0015 mole of $Pb(NO_3)_2$ was dissolved in sufficient volume of water and was treated with 0.003 mole of the ligand dissolved in 100 ml of hot ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for about 6 hr on a sand bath. Yellow precipitate of the complex formed which was filtered, washed with water and

ethanol and finally with ether and dried at 130° in an electric oven.

In cases of $SnCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $SbCl_3$ and $BiCl_3$ solutions were made in dil. HCl. For the preparation of Sb(III), Bi(III) and As(V) complexes, metal-ligand ratio used was 1 : 3. The complexes $[Pb(3,4PT5TH)_2(H_2O)_2](NO_3)_2$ and $[Sn(3,4PT5TH)_2(OH)_2]$ were obtained as yellow precipitates. The complexes $[Sn(3,4PT5TH)_2(OH)_2]$, $[Mg(3,4PT5TH)_2(H_2O)_4]Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$, $[Sb(3,4PT5TH)_2Cl_2]$, $[Bi(3,4PT5TH)(H_2O)Cl_2]$ and $[As(C_{11}H_{13}N_4OS)_2]$ were obtained from the filtrate on crystallisation. All of them were yellow in colour. In case of the Mg(II)-complex, a pH=8 was maintained using dil. NH_4OH .

The following analytical results were obtained for these complexes.

Compounds	Analytical data - Found (Calcd.)			
	%O	%H	%N	%M
$[Pb(3,4PT5TH)_2(H_2O)_2](NO_3)_2$	26.2 (25.2)	1.7 (2.2)	18.3 (19.4)	30.4 (29.6)
$[Mg(3,4PT5TH)_2(H_2O)_4]Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$	32.8 (31.2)	4.6 (4.1)	19.2 (20.7)	4.0 (4.4)
$[Sn(3,4PT5TH)_2(OH)_2]$	33.7 (33.1)	3.4 (2.8)	21.5 (22.0)	22.8 (23.4)
$[Sn(3,4PT5TH)_4(OH)_2]$	42.5 (40.0)	3.4 (3.0)	27.2 (26.0)	13.1 (13.8)
$[Sb(3,4PT5TH)_2Cl_2]$	29.8 (29.0)	2.6 (2.1)	21.1 (20.0)	21.0 (20.8)
$[Bi(3,4PT5TH)(H_2O)Cl_2]$	18.0 (16.4)	1.5 (1.5)	9.5 (10.9)	40.0 (40.8)
$[As(C_{11}H_{13}N_4OS)_2]$	50.4 (50.0)	5.2 (4.9)	22.9 (21.2)	5.9 (5.6)

Results and Discussion

The analytical results indicate that the complexes have the following stoichiometries :

- (1) $\text{Pb}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2 \cdot 2\text{NO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- (2) $\text{Sn}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2 \cdot 2\text{OH}$
- (3) $\text{Sn}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_4 \cdot 2\text{OH}$
- (4) $\text{Mg}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- (5) $\text{Sb}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2$
- (6) $\text{Bi}(3,4\text{PT5TH})\text{Cl}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- (7) $\text{As}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{OS})_2$

The presence of ionic nitrate is indicated by the presence of a very strong absorption band at 1380 cm^{-1} and a medium band at 830 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectrum of the complex. Ionic nitrates generally exhibit¹⁰⁻¹⁴ a very strong band in the region of $1380\text{--}1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a medium band in region of $840\text{--}815\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This complex, thus may be formulated as $[\text{Pb}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$.

The magnesium complex was shaken with aqueous Na_2CO_3 solution thoroughly and the aqueous extract was filtered, acidified with dilute HNO_3 and when treated with AgNO_3 gave precipitation of total chlorine as AgCl . Thus, it may be formulated as $[\text{Mg}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. In case of Sb- and Bi-complexes, no such precipitation of AgCl occurred. Thus they contain covalently bonded chlorine and may be formulated as $[\text{Sb}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Bi}(3,4\text{PT5TH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}_3]$.

The Sn-complexes contain covalently bonded hydroxyl groups because they do not give brown precipitate of Ag_2O when shaken with AgNO_3 solution. Hence they may be formulated as $[\text{Sn}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2(\text{OH})_2]$ and $[\text{Sn}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_4(\text{OH})_2]$ respectively. The presence of coordinated hydroxyl group is also confirmed by the presence of a medium infrared band at 545 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\nu_{\text{Sn-OH}}$ in the former complex and at 542 cm^{-1}

in the latter complex. Further, ν_{OH} band is found to be considerably shifted to 3080 cm^{-1} indicating strong H-bonding of the hydroxyl-hydrogen atom. As indicated in Table 1, bonding of the ligand only through the sulphur atom of the ligand is present in the two Sn(II) complexes. Thus, a four coordinated tetrahedral and 6 coordinated octahedral structures may be tentatively assigned to $[\text{Sn}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2(\text{OH})_2]$ and $[\text{Sn}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_4(\text{OH})_2]$ respectively.

In the tin complex, $[\text{Sn}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_4(\text{OH})_2]$ also, the ν_{OH} is observed to be considerably red shifted to 3100 cm^{-1} region indicating intense hydrogen bonding in the coordinated hydroxyl groups. These two Sn(II) complexes may have *trans* configuration because the presence of only one $\nu_{\text{Sn-OH}}$ band indicates that both the $-\text{OH}$ groups are in identical environment. *Trans*- $[\text{Sn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{phthalocyanine})_2]$ complex also shows only one $\nu_{\text{Sn-OH}}$ band at 563 cm^{-1} in its infrared spectrum¹⁵ and it has an octahedral structure. $\nu_{\text{Sn-OH}}$ band in many other Sn(II) complexes have been reported in the literature and they fall in the region¹⁶⁻¹⁸ of $492\text{--}545\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This observation is in good agreement with the present position of $\nu_{\text{Sn-OH}}$ band at 542 and 545 cm^{-1} in the two Sn(II) complexes respectively.

Infrared spectra and nature of bonding : The infrared spectrum of the ligand contains no absorption band above 3200 cm^{-1} . This indicates intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the ligand molecule. The thioamide bands I, II, III and IV are observed at 1570 , 1200 , 960 and 850 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectrum of the ligand. A sharp band in the spectrum of the ligand is observed at 810 cm^{-1} which is most probably because of 4-substituted pyridine¹⁹. The thioamide band I observed at 1570 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand is a mixed band having contributions from $\delta_{\text{NH}} + \delta_{\text{C-H}}$. In all

TABLE 1—THIOAMIDE BANDS IN cm^{-1}

Compounds	Thioamide bands				Remarks
	I	II	III	IV	
$3,4\text{PT5TH}^{24}$	1570mb	1200	960s	850mb	—
$[\text{Au}(3,4\text{PT5T})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_n$	1580m	1210m 1215s	960s	850mb	Bonding through N only ²⁴
$[\text{Tl}(3,4\text{PT5T})]_n$	1580m	1210m 1220s	960s	850mb	Bonding through N only ²⁴
$[\text{Co}(3,4\text{PT5T})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	1605m	1210w 1240w	990w 1000m	800m	Bonding through N and S both ²⁴
$[\text{Pb}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$	1640s 1610s	1210m 1245m	990w 1010vs	745m	Bonding through S only
$[\text{Sn}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2(\text{OH})_2]$	1590m 1630s	1205m 1230s	970s 1010w	725m	Do
$[\text{Sn}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_4(\text{OH})_2]$	1590m 1630m	1200sh 1215sh 1230s	970s 1010w	725w	Do
$[\text{Mg}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	1590s 1630s	1220sh 1230m	975s 1010m	740m	Do
$[\text{Sb}(3,4\text{PT5TH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	1590m 1630s	1200s 1230s	970s 1010w	725m	Do
$[\text{Bi}(3,4\text{PT5TH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}_3]$	1600m 1640s	1210m 1220w	970s 1010w	730w	Do
$[\text{As}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{OS})_2]$	1590m 1660m	1220sh 1230s	970s 1010w	755	Do

the complexes, this band has become split and one band has blue shifted by 20 cm^{-1} while the other has blue shifted by 60 to 70 cm^{-1} . As bonding through nitrogen is expected to red shift the thioamide band I, it may be suggested that bonding has not occurred through nitrogen of the N-H group in the complexes.

The red-shifting of the $\nu_{C=S}$ band from 850 cm^{-1} in the ligand to 830 cm^{-1} in these complexes also support the bonding of the ligand through sulphur only. This has also resulted in splitting and blue shifting of the thioamide bands II and III of the ligand because of increase in C=N bond order due to coordination through sulphur (Table 1). Thus, the structures suggested for tin complexes are quite reasonable and tetrahedral structure of Pb(II) complex and octahedral structure of Mg(II) complex containing sulphur bonded two 3-(4-pyridyl)triazoline-5-thione ligand molecules and coordinated water may be tentatively suggested.

The octahedral structures and triangular bipyramidal shape of As(V), Sb(III) and Bi(III) complexes is in accord with the sp^3d^2 -hybridisation of the metal orbitals. One of the hybrid orbitals accommodates a lone pair.

The presence of coordinated water molecules in Pb, Mg and Bi-complexes is indicated by the presence of ν_{H_2O} band at 3400 cm^{-1} in Pb- and the Mg-complexes and at 3540 cm^{-1} (medium) in Bi-complex.

This is in good agreement with the position of coordinated water molecules²⁰⁻²³ reported in literature. The presence of free H_2O molecule in Mg(II)-complex is indicated by the fact that the free water molecule is lost on heating above 120° .

The positions of and shifts in thioamide ir bands of ligand and complexes of known structures and of the present complexes are given in Table 1. A comparison of these data clearly indicate that the present complexes are bonded through sulphur only.

This observation is in agreement with the previous work²⁵⁻²⁸.

Metal-ligand vibrations: In the far infrared regions the metal-ligand absorption bands are observed: ν_{Sb-O} at 510 cm^{-1} , $Mg-OH_2$ at 600 cm^{-1} , $Pb-OH_2$ at 470 cm^{-1} and $Bi-OH_2$ at 465 cm^{-1} . These assignments are in good agreement with the literature²⁰⁻²².

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